

Role of Er₂O₃ Reinforcement and Milling Duration in Tailoring the Performance of A201 Aluminum Alloy

Salih Bilal ÇETİNKAL^{1*}

¹ Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Selcuk University, Türkiye,

(ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6212-7670>)

*bilal.cetinkal@selcuk.edu.tr

(Received: 12 December 2025, Accepted: 14 December 2025)

(6th International Conference on Scientific and Innovative Studies ICSIS 2025, December 09-10, 2025)

ATIF/REFERENCE: Çetinkal, S. B. (2025). Role of Er₂O₃ Reinforcement and Milling Duration in Tailoring the Performance of A201 Aluminum Alloy, *International Journal of Advanced Natural Sciences and Engineering Researches*, 9(12), 357-362.

Abstract –Aluminum alloys, particularly the A201 grade in the Al Cu family, are widely used in aerospace and defense applications due to their high specific strength and stable mechanical performance at high temperatures. Enriching these alloys with ceramic reinforcements has recently attracted significant attention because it can further enhance strength, hardness, and thermal stability. This study systematically investigated the effects of milling time on the microstructure and mechanical properties of A201 aluminum alloy reinforced with 1 wt% Er₂O₃. A201.0 alloy chips and Er₂O₃ powder were mechanically milled using a planetary ball mill for 1, 2, and 4 hours, followed by hot pressing at 500°C under 180 MPa for 10 minutes to produce samples. Microstructural observations revealed that 1 hour of milling resulted in limited interaction between the matrix and reinforcement, resulting in partial agglomeration and relatively higher porosity. 2 hour milling produced flake like particles that trapped additional pores and negatively impacted densification. However, 4 hour milling resulted in improved particle refinement, increased Er₂O₃ distribution, and decreased porosity, resulting in a more homogeneous and compact structure. Consequently, density values increased from 2.42 g/cm³ (1 hour) to 2.67 g/cm³ (4 hours). Hardness measurements followed a similar trend, increasing from 85 HB to 99 HB; the slight decrease at 2 hours was attributed to increased pore concentration. Overall, the findings indicate that milling time plays a decisive role in determining the structural integrity and mechanical performance of Er₂O₃ reinforced A201 composites. Among the parameters examined, the 4 hour milling time provided the optimal balance between densification, hardness, and microstructural homogeneity.

Keywords – A201, Er₂O₃, Powder Metallurgy, Milling, Microstructure Characterization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Aluminum based alloys play a critical role in advanced engineering applications thanks to their properties such as low density, high specific strength, good thermal conductivity, and excellent corrosion resistance. These alloys are widely used in the automotive, marine, aerospace, construction, and electrical and electronics industries[1, 2]. Within this group, the 2xx series, characterized by its mechanical stability at high temperatures, is particularly important for aerospace and defense applications. A201, a member of the

Al Cu alloy family and strengthened by the addition of silver, is typically produced by casting or extrusion[3]. While this alloy's castability is limited by its low silicon content, its ability to achieve high strength levels makes it attractive for critical components in the defense and aerospace sectors. A201 is typically produced by gravity casting methods such as sand and permanent mold casting, as well as low pressure casting [4, 5].

Improve performance in harsh environments, A201 alloys are often reinforced with ceramic particles such as alumina (Al_2O_3), silicon carbide (SiC) or boron carbide (B_4C)[6-8]. These reinforcements contribute to increased hardness, mechanical strength, and thermal stability, making them suitable for use in high performance fields such as aerospace technologies and the automotive industry. Erbium, a rare earth element with a metallic silver appearance in its elemental form and a pinkish hue in its oxide form, is frequently used in such systems. Erbium oxide (Er_2O_3), with its cubic crystal structure, is known for its high thermal stability and excellent wear resistance. Its remarkable physical properties make it a valuable material in high temperature applications, as well as in optical, electronic, magnetic, and nuclear technologies [9-11].

In addition to traditional casting techniques, reinforcements can be added to A201 alloys through powder metallurgy (PM), a processing method that has gained increasing importance in recent years. While casting based production can lead to defects such as microporosity, segregation, structural heterogeneity, and hot tearing, PM offers the opportunity to produce finer microstructures with improved chemical homogeneity and significantly reduced porosity. Previous studies have shown that PM processed A201 alloys exhibit enhanced yield strength, superior fatigue resistance, and improved creep performance, largely due to controlled particle size and high density sintering[6, 12-14].

In this study, Er_2O_3 reinforced A201 alloy was produced using powder metallurgy. For a fixed reinforcement ratio, the effects of different milling times on the mechanical properties and microstructural evolution of the composite were systematically investigated.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

The matrix material used in this study was the A201.0 alloy, whose chemical composition is presented in Table 1. Er_2O_3 powder, characterized by its physical properties listed in Table 2, was used as the reinforcement phase. A planetary ball mill (RESTCH PM 200) was used to grind and homogenize the A201.0 alloy and Er_2O_3 powders, which were initially in the form of chips. Two grinding flasks were each loaded with 6 g of A201.0 chips and nine grinding balls. A process control agent (methanol) was added to each flask at 0.5 wt%. The mill was operated at 350 rpm in cycles of 5 min rest followed by 5 min grinding. A pre grinding step lasting 30 minutes was carried out to reduce the chip size and prepare it for the main grinding process.

Table 1. Chemical composition of A201.0 alloy

Fe	Si	Mg	Cu	Ti	Mn	Al
0.1	0.05	0.55	4.5	0.25	0.5	Based

Table 2. Physical properties of A201.0 alloy

Fe	Er_2O_3
Density(g/cm^3)	8.64
Form	Chips
Size	<5mm

Following pre grinding, 1 wt% Er_2O_3 was added to each flask. Then, total milling times of 1, 2, and 4 hours were applied under the same operating conditions. After each milling interval, 1.1 g of powder, equivalent to the mass of one grinding ball, was removed from the flask along with one ball. The milled powders were then consolidated by hot pressing at 500°C and 180 MPa for 10 minutes to obtain bulk samples.

Metallographic preparation was performed to examine the internal microstructure of the pressed samples. Milling was performed on a Metkon Forcipol 2V system using 800, 1200, and 2000 grit sandpapers and then polished with a 1 μm alumina suspension. The samples were then cleaned, rinsed with alcohol, dried, and etched for 30 seconds using Keller's reagent. Brinell hardness measurements were performed using a DIGIROCK LC RBOV hardness tester, with three measurements for each sample, applying a load of 4.903 N for a dwell time of 10 seconds. Experimental density values were measured using a Precisa XB 220A density meter based on the Archimedes principle, also in triplicate for each sample.

III. RESULTS

Optical micrographs of the samples produced in this study are shown in Figure 1. As the grinding time in powder metallurgy progresses, cold welding and subsequent fracture occur between the powders, and this cycle repeats. Flaked powders create porosity in the structure, while ground powders provide easier pressability and a less porous structure.

Figure 1. Optical Microscope images of A201 alloy samples (100x)

The density and hardness values obtained from the Er_2O_3 reinforced A201 alloy samples produced in this study are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Hardness and Density results of samples of A201 alloy produced depending on varying grinding time

IV. DISCUSSION

The microstructural and mechanical results collectively demonstrate that milling time plays a decisive role in both particle distribution and the final properties of the Er_2O_3 reinforced A201 composite. Shorter milling times were not sufficient to ensure full interaction between the matrix and reinforcement, resulting in partial aggregation of the Er_2O_3 particles. Compared to the 50 HB hardness typically reported for unreinforced A201 in the literature, the presence of Er_2O_3 resulted in an overall improvement in hardness across all samples[15].

Particles resulting from the 1 hour milling process were relatively well dispersed, and the matrix did not undergo significant plastic deformation. The decrease in Er_2O_3 particle size contributed to an increase in hardness, while the presence of limited microporosity resulted in a relatively low density value.

In contrast, powders milled for 2 hours developed a distinct flake morphology that trapped more pores within the structure. This increase in porosity explains both the slight decrease in hardness and the density value remaining close to the 1 hour sample.

Extending the milling time to 4 hours produced the most homogeneous microstructure. The refined powder morphology resulted in a significantly less porous structure. It is thought that Er_2O_3 acts as a barrier restricting grain growth, contributing to the increased hardness through the Hall Petch strengthening mechanism. Longer milling times increased the contact area between the matrix and reinforcement, facilitating diffusion processes during sintering and thus improving densification.

In general, as milling time increased, particle refinement and distribution improved significantly, resulting in higher density and hardness. While microstructural integrity was not fully achieved in 1 2 hours, 4 hour milling offered the best combination of homogeneous particle distribution, effective matrix deformation, and improved sintering behavior.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that milling time has a critical effect on the microstructure, density, and hardness of Er₂O₃ reinforced A201 composites produced by powder metallurgy.

- The addition of Er₂O₃ generally increased both hardness and density compared to unreinforced A201.
- Density increased with longer milling times: the lowest value was measured in the 1 hour sample (2.42 g/cm³), followed by 2.57 g/cm³ in the 2 hour sample, and the highest density (2.67 g/cm³) was achieved after 4 hours of milling. This improvement is attributed to particle refinement during sintering, better mixing, and more efficient densification.
- Hardness values were also strongly influenced by milling time. The 1 hour sample reached 85 HB, while the 2 hour sample reached a slightly lower hardness of 81 HB due to porosity associated with the flake particles. The 4 hour milling process achieved a maximum hardness of 99 HB, primarily due to particle refinement and improved interfacial bonding.
- While the 1 hour milling step provided preliminary homogenization, it did not provide sufficient densification. The 2 hour milling interval increased porosity and reduced mechanical performance. The 4 hour milling time produced the most homogeneous microstructure, resulting in the highest hardness and density. Therefore, 4 hour milling was determined to be the most effective processing parameter for producing high performance Er₂O₃ reinforced A201 composites.

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